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Robust community detection based on improved user interaction, enhanced local path index and pattern mining in social networks

Abstract: Community detection in online social networks leads to identifying hidden structures. Combining user interactions and network topology improves community detection accuracy in social networks. We propose a robust Community Detection method based on improved user Interaction degree, enhanced Local Path index and Vertical pattern mining (CDILPV). Our method architecture includes three layers: data processing, community creation and community development. The community creation layer identifies the influential users based on eigenvector centrality and extracts the users, who interact most with them, using vertical pattern mining. For community development, we introduce a measure to calculate the degree of user interaction based on the local clustering coefficient enhanced by the interactions between common neighbors. In addition, we provide two strategies for user membership in the community. First, we calculate the user direct membership degree based on the direct connection degree with the community users and the improved user interaction degree as the weight of connections. Second, if there is no direct connection between the user and the community users, we consider their communication paths. In this way, we propose a hybrid metric to calculate the user indirect membership degree based on the structural index and the improved user interaction degree. Our proposed method based on evaluation with some indices in two datasets, performs better than other methods in accuracy and robustness.

Keywords: Online social network, Community detection, User interaction, Network topology, Pattern Mining, Similarity Measure

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